

MASTERU OF CREATING POETIC SYMBOLS IN LYRICS

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Abstract.

In world literature, modernism represents the system of non-classical views in the field of philosophy, art and literature, invites the reader to the creative process and activates his receptive-aesthetic ability, the main source of the poetics of the open work, many studies have been conducted on its essence.

It is known that in the second half of the 19th century, the flow of modernism continuously renewed the forms in art and literature in the West. came to the field based on the principles of going, abandoning the old and exhausted methods of artistic creation, new ways of thinking and expression, intellectual freedom. Later, this stream spread to all areas of human thought, except for the areas of literature and art was eaten and gave impetus to their development.

Keywords: World scientific and theoretical, thinking priority, relevance, research, phenomenon, aesthetic thinking, national traditions, world literature

INTRODUCTION

The world's scientific-theoretical thinking is in the process of further development the phenomenon of modernism with its stylistic and ideological diversity The world of the 20th century is sharply different from the literature of the previous periods became a leader in aesthetic thinking. Modernism is objective in literature instead of an image of reality, its artistic model in the imagination of the creator aims to create. That is, it is not a reflection of reality in this place, self-expression of the creator takes priority.

The history of the penetration of modernism trends from world literature and its In this regard, there is a need to analyze the post-independence situation and the need to conduct research based on new approaches determines the relevance of the topic. New perspectives in Uzbek literature during the years of independence system was formed, creative freedom for artists, with national traditions as well as new styles and approaches in world literature cases of scientific and creative mastering, art, and research formed.

Therefore, in the poetry of the period of independence, the world is poeticized in a new way perception has risen to a new level, Uzbek poets are world literature artistic taste, aesthetic thinking, being aware of its differences went on the path of renewal. After all, —...attention to literature and art, culture|| First of all, it is important to pay attention to our people and our future as our poet Cholpon said, if literature and culture live, the nation lives It is important that we have absolutely no right to forget that it is possible successful completion of the task is today's main requirement

MATERIALS AND METHODS

20th century literature with its stylistic and ideological diversity It differs sharply from the literature of all periods. Exactly the end of the 19th and 20th centuries people's perception of

the world in Europe and America at the beginning of the century and there was a decisive turn in his attitude to existence. In Turkestan, he began to show its influence on creativity after the First World War. By this time, European and Russian art was new and unique had acquired some characteristics. Throughout its long history art has gone through many crises, but this is the latest change could not be considered as one of the previous recessions. Art is its own From the ideal of classic refinement, it fell back and recognized changed irrevocably.

It was taken from the website of literary scholar D. Kuronov the following idea justifies it: Modernism (fr. moderne - the newest, modern) - a term popularized in the late 19th - early 20th centuries, art and non-realistic currents that appeared after the decadence in literature understood as a common name. Of course, literature and art are wide This phenomenon did not appear in a vacuum, but its buds already existed.

The original artistry was never public. Such art is for everyone neither understandable nor acceptable to everyone. Soviet ideology under the influence of art, not as art, but as a continuation of life, as part of it used to look at. No longer like life, no longer reflecting it, but real works of art that are considered a new aesthetic in their own right began to be created. For this, to do experiments in artists, the ability to conduct tests, research, make mistakes and correct them should be.

Modernist world One of the most important differences between perception and expression is that any event, any of its elements and components (as in realism) as a result of historical development, at the same time, higher than the principle of historicity, as a metaphysical phenomenon understood. Such a relationship is like reality - original reality, time - eternity based on the most basic modernist contradictions. Modernism first appeared in poetry. Indeed, P. Eluard (1895-1952) and French poets such as L. Aragon (1897-1982) were the leading figures of surrealism.

But in a modern style Prose in relation to poetry - "In Search of Lost Time" by M. Proust (—V poiskakh utrachennogo vremeni||), J. Joyce's Ulysses, F. Kafka's Castle The priority of (—Zamok||) novels is obvious. These are novels gave birth to a generation called "lost" in literature. It was born as a response to the events of the First World War. In them the spiritual, spiritual and abnormal conditions of a person were analyzed.

This the common aspect of the works is that in them the French philosopher, "Consciousness" discovered by Henri Bergson (1859-1941), a representative of intuitionism flow analysis method is widely used. One of the common characteristics of modernism is that it is objective instead of an image of reality, its artistic model in the imagination of the creator aims to create. That is, it is not a reflection of reality in this place, Self-expression of the artist is a priority is enough.

It makes sense to bring subjectivity to the fore in creativity superimposition of intuitive knowledge over cognition, in the inner world of man paying particular attention to transient unbridled turns The creative thinking of a creative person and the reality it reflects is unique to be understood as a phenomenon, to limit one's thoughts to any (spiritual, moral, political, etc.) recognition of the right to expression without restrictions is also a characteristic of modernism. Creative freedom is completely inviolable not only in ideological content, but also in formal research. This is the case the structure of the artistic image in modernism, subjective and objective of the work organization, narrative style, plot-composition construction, language features - in short, form peculiarities appear at all levels of the literary work

came. Uzbek The desire for modernity in literature is more evident in poetry. In the Uzbek poetry of the 70s and 80s of the 20th century, a number of artists are modern they were able to do experiments. The first reason for this is man, especially if there is a desire for innovation in the nature of a creative person, the second modernized the moods of dissatisfaction with the social system of that time was embodied in style. The influence of modern poetry, especially Cholpan, poets like Fitrat, A. Mukhtar, R. Parfi, A. Qutbiddin, Fakhrièr felt stronger in his work.

It so happened that Cholpon said in his "The soul is looking for something new". in his essays, Fitrat in his —Adabièt rules to Turkish poetry they began to say that they needed to be updated. An example of Fitrat's universal poem is "Why?" the heart seems to surpass the traditional borders of the poem the expression of the expression seems to have taken on a new form leaves:

Сен келгач,
Кунглимни кайгулар-ла,
Мотамлар-ла ураган
Кора калин пардалар йиртилди

It seems that only sketching the mental landscape, to the conditions characteristics of modern poetry, such as gesture, allusion to feelings Fitrat also gave three in his poetry. Some of his poems yourself you create meaning. You will become an active creator. It's not new versus old, the tradition that was rooted in the old one, that you have opened now. This A poet can't follow the tradition on purpose, but he claims a new way of thinking cannot deny.

RESULTS

When it comes to modern Uzbek poetry, Askad Mukhtar it is necessary to pay special attention to his poetry. Askad Mukhtar is the second of the 20th century in half, new tones, new expression and style of expression to modern poetry began to introduce. How many poems about friendship in literature, odes, completed.

One of our artists is the talented poet Rauf Parfi from the poets who were able to raise modern poetry to a new level. Its unique poetic observation style in our poetry to the level of a special creative school rose. In almost all poems of the sensitive poet, human will and freedom is sung and hate is felt for those who attacked this man.

For example, let's pay attention to the last couplet of Victor Hara's poem It is known that Chilean singer-poet Victor Hara is Augusto Pinoche from the central stadiums of Santiago led by the Junta in one, for singing the song of freedom, the hymn of freedom, his avenger Because of his poems, five thousand prisoners cut their paws, then their hand killed.

A number of R. Parfi's poems are related to colors we can find many epithets. The poet's "Horizon is wounded Alvan". Tolgonar", "The white snow is gray and white", "Youth is the blue season, it passed, it flowed" In his poems, the entire lyrical picture is the quality of images and colors understood through Adjectives beyond their usual meaning rises to the level of an epithet-metaphor with its thin and thin logic. Metaphor is a universal phenomenon of literature, any word category is in place, but it can come in different figurative meanings. In metaphor, especially in metaphors in the poems of our modern poets characteristics unique to the lyric: the world is special, unusually bright, elegant, seeing in black and white, irrational forms, mysterious, feeling strange, unconscious tones, giving a different quality, piece imagination is evident in the images. So, the idea in modern poetry concise, as in aphorisms, it

is possible to express it through few words hide it under the text and derive it from the general idea of the poem The strength of the need to release itself is a metaphorical way of thinking requires

Бахиер булишим мумкин эмиш,
Шундай езилганмиш пешонамга,
Лекин мен укиелмадим,
Уша езувни,
Кузгуга карадим,
Пешонамга кезилганлари
Тескари куринар эди кузгудан

Poet, no matter how many times a person tries, no matter how many predictions he believes, the age-old saying that he cannot change his destiny the truth came to consciousness with the support of a suitable metaphor, unnaturally it only expresses through experience-image.

DISCUSSIONS

Poets and poets who create in the direction of modernism are from the very beginning examples of folklore in his works, myths, ancient legends, used their narrations. Especially J. Joyce, F. Kafka, T. Mann we can see the priority of this aspect in the works of artists. Similarly, in modern Uzbek literature, there are examples of folklore appeal is strong. In particular, R. Parfi, A. Qutbiddin, mythical in the works of Fakhriè images, images in myths and legends are subject to different interpretations. It is important to note that the image of these characters is based on universal values, that he poetically interpreted the national mentality in a unique modern expression is significant with

All modernism works of art affected its components. Artistic language, visual means, including weight, rhyme, image system. These changes, updates are ongoing, getting a new look. Uzbek modern poetry has a history of almost a century. During this period, its specific the theoretical foundations became stricter. Today, these are changes, updates the tradition continues. Attention to the work of prominent representatives of our modern poetry If we look at it, the modern direction, that is, the examples of modern poetry are traditional poetry more or less expressed in the works of poets who created on the way found Sh. Rahman, U. Azim, A. Suyun are also modern in their work taking into account the occurrence of poems, the last decade of the 20th century to witness the rise of the status of non-traditional poetry in the years it is possible.. A look at the human heart in modern poetry listens to his heart. Modernism to realism in some sources they oppose. In fact, modernism is defined by Bahram Rozimuhammad saying: –Realism cannot be opposed. Realism to modernism opposed only to the current of social realism in Suvrat. Slowly now Slowly now literature is becoming free of politics. Literature has its own politics. Literature moves over the human spiritual world, bodies in the spiritual world establishes discipline among them, it has been so since ancient times.

It is not for nothing that the Sufis' doctrine of soul care is on the agenda places. We must walk this way. This is the way to our spirituality This road takes the heart of our nation to the east World science, having integrated the experiences into the spirituality of our grandfathers shows off to the people. So, in new poetry, metaphor, metonymy, qualification the density, density of animation and other image means, some the construction of poems from beginning to end on this basis - without listening to them it invites to read and sleep, to think, to reflect, which is in the spirit poems also belong to the category of works that are difficult to digest,

therefore, these work it would be more correct to call it intellectual poetry. Thought in traditional poetry

He said that feelings follow, and in modern poems, feelings follow thought we can come to a reasonable conclusion.

CONCLUSION

Democratic changes observed on the eve of independence Uzbek to its creators with examples of modernist currents in world literature in addition to getting to know each other better, it also gave an opportunity to create. In this way, especially the new look of our national traditions along with interpretations, translated from foreign languages the works gave great support to Uzbek artists. 20th century modern poetry of N. Hikmat, P. Neruda, P. Eluard, G. Lorca, Jacques Priver, Henri The works of such famous representatives as Mino, B.Posternak, A.Voznesensky His translations had a great impact on Uzbek poetry.

Modernist metaphor has a multi-layered structure. Modernism In his lyrics, he is somewhat "grown-up, multi-subjective, and more after that." Leveled metaphor has a new task - the function of text organization took over. Such a structure gives rise to different sleep and only one resists directional interpretation. R. Parfi, Fakhrièr, It is the basis of the structure of most of A. Qutbiddinlar's poems constitutes a metaphor.

The development of the Uzbek sonnet in the last quarter of the 20th century, R. Parfi, Closely associated with the name of modernist poets such as Fakhrièr. It's them to see the world characteristic of national artistic thinking in the sonnets of his pen, the way of understanding and explanation has been decided. This is a poetic language in the works of poets It took the form of an experiment, not an idea, but an idea spawning combinations began to emerge. In short, modern poems in Uzbek poetry are not only changes in form and content, but a turn to poetry of the heart in verse. that the tradition has arisen, in the way of thinking of our poets confirming that modernist features were more prominent is a legitimate literary phenomenon

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